

Added effect of Schroth's three dimensional exercise on Lung capacity and Cardiopulmonary Endurance in post-TB Pneumonectomy with Obstructive Airway Disease - A Case Report

Dr. Krina Parekh(PT)¹, Dr. Swati Nerkar(PT)², Dr. Shradha Deshpande (PT)³

¹MPT Cardiovascular and Respiratory Physiotherapy – MPT Scholar, K. J. Somaiya College Of Physiotherapy, Sion, Mumbai

²Assistant Professor, K. J. Somaiya College Of Physiotherapy, Sion, Mumbai

³Associate Professor, K. J. Somaiya College Of Physiotherapy, Sion, Mumbai

Abstract - Background of the study- A 49 year old male underwent pneumonectomy post-TB 42 years ago and recently has complaints of breathlessness after walking for 5 minutes and stair climbing (MMRC grade 2) since past 6 months and is diagnosed with obstructive airway disease. He is currently on bronchodilators, antibiotics and inhalers.

Aim of the study is to find out the added effect of Schroth's three dimensional exercises on lung capacity and cardiopulmonary endurance in post-TB pneumonectomy patient with OAD

Objective: To assess cardiopulmonary endurance by using 6MWT, FSS, BDI, TDI and lung capacity by using PFT, breath hold time.

Methodology: Patient undergoes Schroth's three dimensional exercises along with pulmonary rehabilitation for one hour per day, three times a week for 4 weeks.

Results/ Discussion- After 4 weeks, the outcome measures were reassessed and were compared with pre-interventional assessment of the same and a significant difference was found in all of them. 6 minute walk distance percentage increased by 2.58% without any rest pauses. FSS score decreased from 38/63 to 31/63 (fatigue level reduced). BDI scoring – Functional impairment –grade3; magnitude of task – grade1; magnitude of effort –grade2. TDI scoring – Functional impairment - from grade0 to +2; magnitude of task –from grade 0 to +1; magnitude of effort – from grade -1 to 0. PFT values improved with respect to FEV1, FVC AND FEV1/FVC. Breath hold time increased from 13 seconds to 17 seconds.

Conclusion- The results suggests that Schroth's three dimensional exercises along with pulmonary rehabilitation is found to be effective on lung capacity in post-TB pneumonectomy with OAD

Keywords- post-TB pneumonectomy, obstructive airway disease, Schroth's three dimensional exercise, lung capacity, cardiopulmonary endurance, 6MWT, FSS, BDI, TDI, PFT, breath hold time

1)Introduction:

A 49 year old male underwent left pneumonectomy post-TB 42 years ago and recently has complaints of breathlessness after walking for 5 minutes and stair climbing (MMRC grade 2) since past 6 months and is diagnosed with obstructive airway disease. He is currently on bronchodilators, antibiotics and inhalers.

The patient is also presented with a shift of mediastinum and trachea towards left side with compensatory hyperinflation of the right lung and right – sided scoliosis.

Schroth's three dimensional exercises include rotational breathing technique which helps in improving chest wall mobility.

One of the study conducted on patients with idiopathic scoliosis have proved that using Schroth's three dimensional exercise along with respiratory muscle exercises have improvement on pulmonary function.^[1]

Case history:

Patient was apparently alright but since last 2.5 years he experiences breathlessness on exertion, cough with greenish expectoration (teaspoon) 5-6 times in a day. He visited his family doctor for the same and xray was suggested which revealed pleural effusion and was further suggested to do CT scan. CT scan was done and was normal. Then he was referred to a lung specialist where blood test, 2D Echo, HR CT was advised.

His investigations showed:

1)PFT - very severe obstruction (FEV1/FVC:55 , FVC: 1.75 , FEV1 : 0.79)

2)CT Scan revealed - post pneumonectomy status with resultant loss of left hemithorax, shift of trachea and mediastinum towards left with crowding of ribs and upward shift of left hemidiaphragm and compensatory hyperinflation of right left lung parenchyma with retrosternal herniation.

- thin fibrotic strands in apical and posterior segment of right upper lobe, superior segment of right lower lobe and fibroatelectasis changes in anterior segment of right upper lobe and medial segment of right middle lobe.

-Areas of bronchiectasis with peribronchial thickening in right upper lobe.

-Mild bronchial prominence with peribronchial thickening involving rest of the segmental and subsegmental bronchi of right bronchial tree

-Multiple discrete and confluent centrilobular nodules with few forming "VY" branching pattern (tree in bud appearance), few forming small areas of consolidations in right lung parenchyma.

Medications were started for him under a chest physician:

MDI forglyn plus, MDI duolin forte rotocaps, Deriphylline retard 300, Tab azee 250mg, Tab wysolone 5mg, Syp zedex plus.

He came with the same complains and for pulmonary rehabilitation to the OPD and was assessed for the same.

2)Assessment:

1)On observation - pallor present

2)Posture -

- posterior - scapular asymmetry - right sided scapula appeared more prominent than left, right side curvature of scoliosis, waist creases are asymmetrical- more creases on the right pelvis
- Anterior - head tilt and rotation present on the right side, shoulder height asymmetry
- Lateral - forward head, rounded shoulders, thoracic kyphosis, anterior pelvic tilt

3)Gait changes -

- stance phase - BOS appears wide, more weight bearing on the right side
- Swing phase - slight reduction in hip flexion of the right leg, the leg is carried forward with a bit of trunk compensation, arm swing reduced, foot clearance - reduced dorsiflexion

4)Auscultatory findings - ronchi was present in all zones

5)On percussion - resonant note on the right side and dull note on the left side

6)Chest expansion - 2.5cm at axillary level, 2cm at nipple level and 2cm at xiphisternal level

7)Chest excursion - reduced on the left side at all levels

8)I : E ratio = 1:2

9)Type of breathing - thoracoabdominal

10)Scar evaluation - post lateral thoracic region on the left side (extending from lat scapular border to mid thoracic region), healing status - adherent, length - 18cm, redness and tenderness - absent

11)Outcome measure -

- 6 minute walk distance - patient completed 49.81% of his predicted distance with one pause of 2min 20seconds
- Breath hold time - 13seconds
- Fatigue severity score - 38/63

3)Methodology:

Patient was enrolled for pulmonary rehabilitation:

Patient undergoes Schroth's three dimensional exercises along with pulmonary rehabilitation for one hour per day, three times a week for 4 weeks.

The intervention was approved by IRB.

Pulmonary rehabilitation included -

Type	Exercises
Breathing exercises	Diaphragmatic breathing, Segmental breathing and thoracic expansion exercise
Aerobic endurance training	Cycling for 10 mins and arm ergometer for 10 mins (with heart rate monitoring - THR = 128 to 143 beats/min for 40% to 60%)
Strength training	B/L UL exercises with 1.5kg dumbbell and B/L LL exercises with 1.5kg weight cuff
Postural correction	thoracic stretching of left side, theraband exercises for lt UL shoulder flexion and shoulder abduction for 5 counts hold - 10 reps

Schroths three dimensional exercise^[1]:

The patient was given exercises in sidelying position and supine position in the starting and after 8 sessions standing exercises were also incorporated.

Stretching the lumbar part	10sec x 15 times
Stretching the thoracic part	10sec x 15 times
Schultergegenzug in sitting	4 set×6 rep
Sprossenheber in sitting	4 set×6 rep
Schultergegenzug in side-lying	4 set×6 rep
Schultergegenzug in prone	4 set×6 rep
Muscle cylinder	4 set×6 rep

The outcome measures that were used to find out the effect of this intervention were by using 6MWD^[2] for cardiopulmonary endurance, FSS^[3] for severity of fatigue, BDI,TDI^[4] for dyspnea and PFT^[5], breath hold time^[6] for lung capacity.

All the outcome measures were assessed on day 1 of the intervention protocol and again the readings were taken at the end of the protocol (week 4) and both the readings were compared.

4)Results:

After 4 weeks, the outcome measures were reassessed and were compared with pre-interventional assessment of the same and a significant difference was found in all of them.

FSS score decreased from 38/63 to 31/63 (fatigue level reduced).

BDI scoring – Functional impairment – grade3; magnitude of task – grade1; magnitude of effort – grade2.

TDI scoring – Functional impairment - from grade0 to +2; magnitude of task – from grade 0 to +1; magnitude of effort – from grade -1 to 0.

Breath hold time increased from 13 seconds to 17 seconds.

6MWD values are given below in Table No.1.

Table No.1

Date	6MWD	Drop in Saturation	No. of pauses	RPE level pre	RPE level post
03-06-25	49.18%	No drop	1 (2min 20sec)	9	13
09-07-25	51.76%	No drop	0	6	13

PFT values improved with respect to FEV1 and FEV1/FVC. (Table No.2)

Table no.2

	FEV1	FVC	FEV1/FVC
09-04-25	0.79	1.75	55
09-07-25	0.85	1.52	55.9

5)Discussion and Conclusion:

Schroths three dimensional exercises are highly used in conditions like idiopathic scoliosis to improve the pulmonary functions.^[7,8]

Schroths three dimensional exercises are considered to be more effective than manual treatments because they are three - dimensional. It requires a patient to recognize the 3D changes and restore the spinal structure and function by correcting the trunk. It consists of rotational angular breathing which uses the rotation of the deformed rib with breathing.^[9]

For patients with scoliosis, breathing expanding the thorax and diaphragmatic breathing corrects the pattern of breathing and increases the mobility of the thorax and functions of the lungs.^[9]

The results suggests that combination of Schroth's three dimensional exercises and pulmonary rehabilitation is found to be effective on lung capacity in post-TB pneumonectomy with OAD.

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